

IPBES VA Ch2. Systematic review of indigenous and local knowledge and philosophies / IPBES values assessment (2.2)

Code: IPBES_VA_ 2.2

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Description

This literature review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. To respond to mandate that the IPBES scoping document for the values assessment has for chapter 2, regarding the assessment of “the coverage of diverse conceptualizations of values with regard to nature and nature’s benefits to people” that should draw on “qualitative case studies associated with indigenous and local knowledge (ILK)”, a literature search and review was conducted as part of the stage 2 of the literature review strategy for the chapter. The objective of this review was to identify the main trends in academic literature regarding the conceptualization of values by indigenous peoples and local communities (IPLC) in order to inform different sections of the chapter concerning worldviews, human-nature relationships, value types, power, justice, sustainability, institutions, and languages. Chapter 2’s stage 2 is a way to incorporate other sources of evidence appropriate for each section and subsection, with searches tailored to specific questions that allow to obtain a broader and deeper database to fulfil the mandate of the scoping document. This review was done following FPIC principles.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** Systematic review for articles published in Scopus until the date of the search
- **Search languages:** English
- **Search engine:** Scopus
- **Exact search date:** August 11, 2020
- **Search terms:**
TS= (TITLE-ABS-KEY (Indigenous OR Local) AND (Pastoralis* OR herder OR fisher* OR hunt* OR forest* OR agriculture OR livelihood OR nomad OR land* OR river* OR sea OR ocean OR mountains) AND (knowledge OR philosophy) AND (values) AND (nature OR Mother Earth OR biodiversity OR ecosystem))
- **Sample extracted (A):** 252 references (A)
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Authors
 - Author(s) ID
 - Title
 - Year
 - Source title
 - Volume
 - Issue
 - Art. No.
 - Page start
 - Page end
 - Page count
 - Cited by
 - DOI
 - Link
 - Affiliations
 - Authors with affiliations
 - Abstract
 - Author Keywords
 - Index Keywords
 - Document Type
 - Publication Stage
 - Access Type
 - Source
 - EID
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.2_11- 08-2020_(A).csv

Screening criteria based on expert knowledge was applied to the raw references to select the relevant files to the review (**R1**). This resulted in the 193 screened references in file (**B**).

- **Sample extracted:** 193
- **Fields extracted (B):**
 - Authors
 - Author(s) ID
 - Title

- Year
- Source title
- Volume
- Issue
- Art. No.
- Page start
- Page end
- Page count
- Cited by
- DOI
- Link
- Affiliations
- Authors with affiliations
- Abstract
- Author Keywords
- **Location and format of the data (B):** IPBES_VA_2.2_09-2020_(B).csv
- **Treatment applied (R1):** Title and abstract were analysed based on expert knowledge. This led to selecting relevant records for the review.

To begin with the coding process, PDFs in English, Spanish, Portuguese and German were retrieved for 183 references of the 193 in **(B)**. For 8 references the PDF was not available and for two, PDFs were in Arabic and Hungarian, and in consequence, coding was not possible.

The 183 full papers in **(C)** were coded using **(R2)** (35 codes).

- **Sample extracted:** 183
- **Fields extracted (C):**
 - ID/Number
 - PDF
 - Coded by
 - Author
 - Title
 - Year
 - Abstract
 - Journal
 - Link or DOI
- **Location and format of the data (C):** IPBES_VA_2.2_09-2020_(C).csv
- **Treatment applied (R2):** 183 PDFs were fully read and coded according to **(R2)**.

Once the coding process was finalised, 150 references were found relevant for informing chapter 2. These were saved in **(D)**.

- **Sample extracted:** 150
- **Fields extracted (D):**
 - ID/Number

- PDF
- Coded by
- Author
- Title
- Year
- Abstract
- Journal
- Link or DOI
- **Location and format of the data (D):** IPBES_VA_2.2_10-2020_(D).csv

Quantitative and qualitative analysis of the coded information was compiled in the report found in **(E)**.

After analyses were completed, one new record was added with the purpose of complementing information. This decision was based on expert knowledge. Full reference of this record can be found in **(F)**.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.2_08-2020_(A)	csv	951 KB	Database with the list of 252 references retrieved from the Scopus search
B	IPBES_VA_2.2_09-2020_(B)	csv	650 KB	Database with the list of 193 references selected after screening title and abstract
C	IPBES_VA_2.2_09-2020_(C)	csv	446 KB	Database with the list of 183 references for which PDFs were retrieved, fully read and coded
D	IPBES_VA_2.2_10-2020_(D)	csv	329 KB	Database with the list of 150 references that were found relevant to inform chapter 2
E	IPBES_VA_2.2_11-12_2020_(E)	pdf	563 KB	Report presenting results of the quantitative and qualitative analyses of the coded information
F	IPBES_VA_2.2_12-2020_(F)	txt	202 bytes	Additional reference added for complementing information, based on expert knowledge
R2	IPBES_VA_2.2_09_2020_(R2)	txt	3 KB	List of 35 codes used for reviewing the 183 references enlisted in file C